

Vatsanabha: A Literary Review with its Toxic Effects

Dr. Iyshwarya H.S.¹

¹Assistant Professor, Department of RSBK
Ashwini Ayurvedic Medical College And Research Centre, Tumkur . Karnataka

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Abstract: Ayurveda is one among the oldest treatment modality of medicine carried out in India. Ayurveda deals with both Herbal and mineral drugs along with Mahavisha and upavisha dravyas. Our Acharyas have given us a wonderful way to use the Visha dravyas in the treatment of patients based on appropriate season, Person and in condition of Patient and dose. It is one of the mahavisha varga. This vatsanabha has many indications like jwara, ajeerna, agnimandya, amajeerna, kasa, peenasa, amavata etc diseases where if vatsanabha is done proper shodhana, where its toxic effects are removed and neutralized, then there will be great use. If the drug vatsanabha is used more than the prescribed dose or in excess dose, or if it is not properly purified then aconitum ferox shows its toxic effects.

Keywords: Herbomineral Dravya, Visha Dravya, Aconitum Ferox, Amavata.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is one of the purana chikitsa that is practicing system of medicine in India.⁽¹⁾Ayurveda has its own mode of vision to the science of diseases, diagnosis and its treatment .In Ayurveda vatsanabha or aconitum ferox is one of the commonly used medicine all over country. At 1st the tribal people discovered the poisonous content present in the aconitum ferox as they used this tubers for making the poisonous arrows to kill the animals. ⁽²⁾The word Aconite is derived from a Greek word Akoniton, which means to spear. The usefull part of vatsanabha is kanda that is tubers. In vedic period also we have the 1ST reference of vatsanabha in atharva veda ^(3,4) vatsanabha which is properly purified and used in the prescribed dose ,best results can be attained in amajeerna, Atisara, agnimandya, jwara, kasa, peenasa diseases.⁽⁵⁾Vatsanabha also a good rasayana^(6,7)Vatsanabha is both visha dravya, that is highly toxic hence grouped under mahavisha varga and in the same way also very effective in treatment aspect also as it has vyavayi, vikashi, and ashukari guna in the low dose.

Thus vatsanabha a literary review is made in order to evaluate its pharmacological and well asto deal with its toxic properties.

➤ Know About the Drug Description:

- Botanical name -Aconitum Ferox
- Naturalorder -Ranunculaceae
- English name-Monk's hood.
- Kula-Vatsanabha kula
- Kannada name-Bachanaga
- Hindi name-Bachnag

➤ Synonyms of Vatsanabha:-

Gosthanakara⁽¹¹⁾, Ugram, Mahoushadham, Garalam, Naga, Pranaharakam, Sindhuvara⁽¹⁰⁾ Vatsanabhyaakriti⁽¹²⁾, KandaVisha, Madhura, mahavisham, Nepala Panchangula⁽¹³⁾, Panduram⁽¹⁴⁾ Visham⁽⁹⁾Amritam⁽⁸⁾

- **Upayujya bhaga of vatsanabha:** kanda, tubers.

Prapthi sthana- vatsanabha plant is found in10,000 - 14,000feet of high altitude of Himalaya mountain⁽¹⁵⁾,also found in other areas like Nepal, Sikkim, Assam.

Roopa Parignana:- MORPHOLOGY OF
VATSANABHA स्वरूप

Vatsanabha aconitum ferox is a herb which grows up to a height of 1 to 2 feet. Leaves are just likethe leaves of palm with sharp cut edges which are irregular in nature, colour is light green which has a long petiole. It has elongated flowers which are neela varna blue in colour. Roots are two in number which has two tubers which measures up to half inches in length and one inch in diameter. Roots are broad in the basal part and tapering in the end part. Fruits are long sturdy and having hair like structures on them, beeja of vatsanabha are blackish brown in color. kanda resembles the shape of Go sthana means Cow's udder.

II. VARIETIES

Based on the colour ,in market Vatsanabha is found in 2 color: (1) Shwetha (white) (2) Krishna(black) (3) Aconitumferox:- it is mahavisha that is toxic in nature but after proper purification used in treatment of different diseases etc. **Aconitumheterophyllum:**Found in Himalayas,contains an alkaloid called Atisineandalsoh as therapeutic activity. **AconitumChasmanthum:-**Tuberis blackishbrown in colour.Active Alkaloid isIndaconitine.**Aconitumdeinorrhizum:**Tuberishardin consistency and contains alkaloids such as aconitene and pseudo aconitene. **Aconitumbalfourii:-** this species can be found in higher altitude at 10,000-14,000ft height in Himalayan regionwhich is bitter in taste, and cause tingling sensation in the tongue due to contain Pseudo Aconitene as an alkaloid.

Vatsanabha tubers are collected during spring or winter season and collectedonly when the fruits gets ripened in the plant. (Phala Pakkvottaram)

➤ *Gunakarma: (RajaNighantu)*

- Rasa(taste)—Madhura (tasteless or sweet)
- Vipaka—Madhura
- Guna—rooksha, laghu, vyavayi, vikasi,ashukari
- Veerya — Ushna
- Karma—vedana hara, shwasa hara, kasahara,jwaraghna,kandughna, krimighna, kushtaghna,shoolahara, vedanasthapana.
- Doshagnata – balance of all tridosha.
- Rogagnata— agni mandhya, ajeerna, atisara, kushta,jwara, kasa, shwasa.
- Shodhana Karma⁽¹⁵⁾(Purification steps of Vatsanabha)

Genuine quality of vatsanabha is procured, Vatsanabha tubers are taken washed to remove physical impurities, and tubers are made into small pieces and dipped in vessel containing gomuti cow's urine. Then the vessel is kept under sunlight for 3 to four days and each day it is replaced with fresh gomutra ,after three to four days Vatsanabha pieces are taken out from the vessel, its outer covering or testa is removed and is kept in clean fore folded cora cloth, Pottali is tied to dolayantra and boiled in goksheera for 1 Prahara (3 hrs), after that pottali is removed aconitum pieces are taken out washed, dried in sunlight, powered and used, through this vatsanabha can be purified according to acharyas.

➤ *Sangrahakaala: Season of Collection of drug:-*

Table 1: Yogas Compound Formulations

Sl.No.	Yogas(formulations)	Rogagnata (Indications)	Text Book
1	Agnitundi Vati	Ama,Ajeerna,Agnimandya	BhaishajyaRatnavali
2	AgniKumararasa	Agnimandya	BhaishajyaRatnavali
3	Ajeernakantakarasa	Ajeerna, ama	Bhavaprakasha
4	Anandabhairairasa	Jwara Kasa Atisara	RasarajaSundara
5	GrahaniKapata rasa	Agnimandya,Atisara	Yogaratanakara
6	GrihaniGajaKesari	Amaatisara , amajeerna	Yogaratanakara
7	Hinguleshwararasa	Shoola hara, shotha hara	BhaishajyaRatnavali
8	KasturibhairavaRasa	Atisara, jwara, vishama	SidhayogaSangraha
9	KaphaketuRasa	Kasa, Peenasa, jwara	RasaTarangini
10	MrutyunjayaRasa	Jwara	RasaTarangini
11	MritaSanjeeviniRasa	Kasa, VishamaJwara, Amavata, shotha	BhaisajyaRatnavali
12	PanchamritaRasa	Peenasa,Rajayakshma,Kasa	RasaRatnaSamucchaya
13	ShwasaKutaraRasa	Shwasa, kaasa	BhaisajyaRatnavali
14	Sanjeevini Vati	Ajeerna,Ajeerna Jwara	SharangadharaSamhita
15	TribhuvanaKeerthirasa	Kasa, Jwara Shwasa	YogaRatanakara

These are few yogas which are frequently used by the practitioners in which aconitum is one of the ingredients.

➤ *Lakshana of visha in Vatsanabha*

- Leaves when rubbed on the skin, which produces tingling sensation and also person feels numbness, and also if the root is held in hand for longer time.
- When the person inhales the smell of the plant shows narcotic effect.
- When vatsanabha comes in contact with eyes there will be shoola of netra and shotha of netra.
- Vatsanabha when ingestion through mouth, there will be burning sensation and tingling sensation from mouth to the stomach.
- Which is followed by excessive salivation, nausea, vomiting and loose stools.
- Person experiences dryness of mouth, thirsty, and later difficulty of swallowing.
- Numbness and tingling sensation is felt over the body.
- Associated with shirahshoola, bhrama, profuse sweating the lower limbs become weak and the person finds difficult in standing and walking.
- The person experiences clonic and tonic movements of convulsions, with severe pain of muscles and cramps.
- The vision becomes dim and there may be diplopia.
- Pupils alternately shows contract and dilatation, but remain dilated in further stages.
- In later stages hypotension takes place, Cardiac arrhythmia with AV block may occur.
- At initial stages there will be tachycardia, but in the further stages bradycardia occurs due to AV block.
- At the end stage there may be marked general muscular weakness, compression in the chest and death takes place due to Paralysis of heart muscles and respiratory organs where there is loss of the function of circulatory and respiratory systems.

➤ *Vatsanabha (aconitum ferox)- visha vegas (toxic effects)⁽¹⁶⁾*

- Ist Vega - twak vikara, skin diseases
- IInd Vega – kampavata, tremors
- IIIrd Vega- daaha, Burning Sensation
- IVth Vega- Aswastha, deviation from normal health
- Vth Vega – lalasarava, excessive Salivation
- VIth Vega- tightness of soft muscles, Twitching of muscles
- VIIth Vega – general muscular weakness, Lethargic
- VIIIth Vega- marana, Death
- **Aushadha matra (Therapeutic Dose)** :- $1/8$ - $1/4$ Ratti mg of tuber or kanda⁽¹⁷⁾ 250 mg of satva, or extract of Aconitum.
- **Maraka maatra (Fatal dose)** :- 1 gm of root 2-5 mg of aconitene.
- **Maraca kaala (Fatal Period)**: 1-8 hours.
- **Chikitsa (Treatment)**: Amashaya Prakshalana stomach wash, followed by Vamana⁽¹⁸⁾ Tankana with Gorgita is the antidote for vatsanabha. Along with Arjuna Twak choorna with Kasthuri and, Arjuna Twak

choorna with Gogrita can be given.

- → According to Modern science the treatment is as follows :- Gastric lavage with warm water⁽¹⁹⁾ with weak solution of iodine in Potassium iodide or tannic acid etc. and Precipitate alkaloid or animal charcoal also can be used to remove the residual poison.
- → Inj Atropine 1/2 to 1 mg can be administered.⁽²⁰⁾
- → later symptomatic treatment can be assigned.
- **Time of administration (Sevana Kala)⁽²¹⁾** :- It can be administered during winter and spring season.
- **Anupana (adjuvant)** :- goghrita, goksheera, sheetala jala, and madhura ahara padartha can be given
- **Contraindications**:- in summer season, one who is baala, vrudha, garbhavastha.
- In the above conditions the usage of aconitum is contraindicated.

III. DISCUSSION

- Vatsanabha is enumerated under mahavisha varga, is also called as Amrutha in Ayurvedic literature acc to acharyas. As well as Vishait is due to Vatsanabha if used in less dose it acts as Amrita in human body by eradicating many diseases such as kasa, shwasa, peenasa, jwara, agnimandya, ama, atisara etc. But the same if use in fatal dose then it may act as Visha and it may cause marana, death also.
- vatsanabha acts as a deadly poison in patients if not properly purified, by creating symptoms like tingling sensation and numbness in tongue and mouth, burning sensation, nausea, vomiting, cardiac arrhythmia, Paralysis of respiratory and cardiac muscles, destroying its functions, later coma and death.
- So aconite while prescribing is cautioned before its internal use. This is advised only after proper purification and in right conditions and to the right patients.
- Vatsanabha, in formulations where used along with antidote that is tankana, doesn't cause any illeffects.
- In conditions like greeshma rutu and in sheeta rutu, aconitum drug is contraindicated may be due to natural aggravation of pitta and vata doshas.
- In baala and in vrudha persons administration of vatsanabha is contraindicated may be due to Vyavayi, Vikasi, ashukari, action which affects the avara satva of persons.
- In garbhavastha condition it may cause harm to the fetus through the mother.
- If aconitum is administered in physical exhaustion condition it may cause further tachycardia and cardiac arrest may take place.
- Thus in order to pacify vatsanabha toxic effects Shodhana of Vatsanabha is carried out in the media, gomutra for 3 to 7 days and Swedana is carried out in the media Godugha for

1 Prahara may Pacifies its toxic effects & Godugdha which is sheeta in nature imparts its therapeutical qualities into the drug by neutralizing the vyavayi, vikasi and ashukari visha qualities of the drug.

- By this we can minimize the adverse drug reaction of the drug only when it is used in therapeutic dose with properly followed all steps of purificatory procedures.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

According to Ayurvedic pharmacopeia there are jangama, sthavara and kruthrima types of visha. Among sthavara visha we have two types, mahavisha and upavisha. Among which vatsanabha comes under mahavisha varga, where these maha visha vargas are more toxic in nature than upa visha vargas. and various measures have been adopted to remove and neutralize the toxic effects of the drug. Then only these drugs become fit for administration when they attained the therapeutic qualities. As the review suggests Vatsanabha which is one of the Ingredient among many formulations, used with caution after imparting therapeutic qualities into the drug. Then only the treatment will be effective and Patients become relief from their symptoms. Thus during the preparation of these compound formulations, standard operating procedure should be adopted during selecting, manufacturing and packing of these medicines. GMP is to be followed during manufacturing of the yogas containing toxic drugs like vatsanabha.

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